

Studies on the Importance of Critical Raw Materials for Long-term and Safe Operation of Nuclear Power Plants

Report from a Short Term Research Mission undertaken for the period 01-28 February 2017 in Centro de Química Estrutural(CQE), Instituto Superior Técnico – Universidade de Lisboa, Lisbon, Portugal, supervised by prof. Maria de Fátima G. Costa Montemor

Ivaylo Naydenov, PhD Student, Department of Thermal and Nuclear Power Engineering, Faculty of Power Engineering and Power Machines, Technical University of Sofia, Bulgaria

I. Background

1. Nuclear power status and development outlook

As of February 2017 there are 449 operational power reactors worldwide with net installed power generating capacity of 392.137 GW, another 60 reactors with net power generating capacity of 60.14 GW being under construction. The total accumulated operational experience amounts to 17,030 reactor-years [16]. The most common reactor type is the pressurized water reactor (PWR) (Figure 1) that uses as a primary circuit coolant light water under pressure, the water acting simultaneously as neutron moderator. These reactors operate in double circuit power plants, the secondary circuit's working fluids being demineralised water and dry saturated steam.

Figure 1. Number of operational power reactors by reactor type as of February 2017 [16]

Between 1985 and 2015 the nuclear generated electricity worldwide increased from 1327.63 TWh to 2441.33 TWh [15]. The nuclear power output for 2015 accounted for 11.2% of world's total electricity supplies [14]. Nuclear power's development between 1985 and 2015 is illustrated on Figure 2. The majority of the energy forecasts are favourable with regards to nuclear energy's development perspectives. The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) estimates that the net installed capacity would be growing, reaching around 404 GW in 2020 and 658 GW in 2050 (average estimations); the IAEA also expects nuclear power generation to be increasing reaching around 2930 TWh in 2020 and 5300 TWh in 2050 (average estimations) [14]. British Petroleum expects that primary energy production from nuclear sources would increase from 583.1 million tonnes of oil equivalent (Mtoe) in 2015 to 725.7 Mtoe in 2020, reaching 859.2 Mtoe in 2035 [1]. United States Department of Energy's Energy Information Administration also forecasts increase in nuclear power generation by 2040 (Figure 3) [30].

The need to cut greenhouse gas emissions from energy production might have a positive impact on nuclear energy's development: its median life-cycle greenhouse gases emissions rate is among the lowest ones – 15 gCO₂-eq/kWh, compared with 7 gCO₂-eq/kWh for hydropower, 16 gCO₂-

eq/kWh for wind power, 49 gCO₂-eq/kWh for photovoltaics, 492 gCO₂-eq/kWh for natural gas, and 1025 gCO₂-eq/kWh for coal [13]. Furthermore, the International Energy Agency estimates that in order to meet its decarbonisation goals, the EU member states need to add 731 GW of renewables and 64 GW of nuclear power to their generating capacity within the 2015-2040 timeframe [18].

Figure 2. Number of power reactors and their net installed capacity [16]

Figure 3. Anticipated structure of world's electricity generation by fuel type [30]

2. Long-term operation of nuclear facilities

The IAEA defines long-term operation of a nuclear power plant as operation beyond an established time frame set forth by, for example, licence, term, design, standards, and regulations, which has been justified by safety assessment, with consideration given to life limiting processes and features of systems, structures and components [17]. The most important objective in nuclear power plants' operation is nuclear safety. Important considerations for defining the acceptable level of safety during long-term operation include:

- the time period of long-term operation;
- the operational history and experience at the plant;
- the physical condition of the plant;
- the ageing of safety-related systems, structures and components;
- the degree of certainty about the long-term performance of safety components [24].

Currently long-term operation is considered worldwide since 64.8% of all power reactors are aged above 30 years. This share nominally represents 291 reactors with net installed capacity of 250.141 GW [16]. The age distribution of the world power reactors fleet is shown on Figure 4. Long-term operation is a viable option to maintain nuclear power's role worldwide and particularly in the countries where it accounts for considerable share in the power generation (around or more than a

fifth). Such countries are Belgium (37.5%), Bulgaria (31.3%), the Czech republic (35.8%), Finland (33.7%), France (76.3%), Hungary (52.7%), Republic of Korea (31.7%), Russia (18.6%), Slovakia (55.9%), Slovenia (38.0%), Spain, (20.3%), Sweden (34.3%), Switzerland (33.5%), Ukraine (56.5%), and the United States (19.5%) [15].

Figure 4. Age distribution of world power reactors [16]

The long-term operation of nuclear power plants must ensure safe operation, manage the effects of ageing, and should provide at least the same extent of nuclear safety as that maintained during the design operational period. The decision to pursue long-term operation is based on the following considerations:

- Strategic elements such as the need for electric power and issues concerning supply diversity;
- Applicable regulatory requirements, including an assessment of the adoption of new requirements;
- A technical assessment of the physical condition of the nuclear power plant, including identification of enhancements or modifications to the physical facility if necessary, and of the impact of changes on nuclear power plant programmes and procedures necessary for continued safe operation;
- A technical assessment of the environmental impact of LTO;
- An economic assessment [17].

3. Critical raw materials (CRM)

Figure 5. Critical raw materials for EU's economy [9]

The European Commission has reviewed 54 non-energy materials which have been identified as important to EU's economy. The materials under consideration include industrial minerals, ores,

biotic materials, and processed or refined materials. The EU methodology used to estimate criticality has a combination of two assessment components: economic importance and supply risk. According to the EU criticality methodology twenty out of fifty four considered materials are classified as critical: antimony, beryllium, borates, chromium, cobalt, coking coal, fluorspar, gallium, germanium, indium, magnesite, magnesium, natural graphite, niobium, platinum group metals, phosphate rock, rare earths, silicon metal, and tungsten. The relationship between economic importance and supply risk for the 54 considered materials is illustrated on Figure 5.

4. Nuclear power applications of CRM

In the modern nuclear power plants (NPPs) with light water reactors more than 25 different main construction metal alloys are applied. Additional materials are present in cement containments, instrumentation, tanks, pumps, support systems, control rods, moderators, neutron poisons, etc. Currently, nuclear power plants' general by-design operational period is 30-40 years, as the tendencies in nuclear power plant developments are focused on the life-time extension. Considerable number of existing reactors has operated for more than 30 years with the outlook for extending their operational life-times to up to 60 years (Figure 4). The new generation of nuclear reactors has to meet the following requirements:

- Longer operational lifetimes – up to, and in some cases, exceeding 60 years;
- Technological efficiency and economic viability;
- Strong focus on safety and reliability [17].

Meeting the abovementioned demands necessitates: (1) improving the construction materials and their components and (2) corrosion control.

In addition to meeting the requirements of long-term operation, materials in nuclear industry have to conform to other requisites concerning their neutron absorption cross-section, service temperature, mechanical properties, neutron radiation resistance, thermal expansion, thermal conductivity, chemical compatibility, etc. High-nickel alloys, zirconium alloys, and stainless steels are used for various applications in nuclear power facilities.

Zirconium alloys (Zircaloy-2, Zircaloy-4, H-1, H-2.5, Zirlo) are used in cladding tubes that isolate the nuclear fuel from the coolant, being the most preferred materials because of high design requirements: low neutron absorption cross-section, high corrosion resistance in a combination with unique mechanical properties. High-nickel alloys are applied mainly for construction of steam-generating pipes (evaporation systems) in nuclear steam generators, reactor vessel elements, welds, etc. The alloys 690 and 800 are preferable because of their general resistivity and stability against stress-corrosion in combination with their excellent mechanical durability. The most used stainless steel is series ASTM 300, which contain about 10 wt. % Ni and 20 wt. % Cr, as well as Mo and Ti. Stainless steels are used because of their good corrosion resistance. They are appropriate construction materials for components in contact with reactor coolant, such as circulating pumps, valves, pipes, heat-exchangers for chemical and volume control, condenser tubes, etc. The suitable properties of these key construction materials are obtained by adding critical raw materials (CRMs), such as Cr, Mo, Si, V, W, Mn, Mg, Nb, Co, Be, etc. Those materials must endure extreme operational conditions – neutron radiation, high temperatures and pressures, oxidizing and/or reduction media, tensions, electrolytic contact, etc. The CRMs used as alloying elements (e.g. Nb, Zr, Cr, W, V, Mo) are prone to supply risks that would have considerable impact on the economy of many European countries. The replacing construction materials would need to meet high requirements in terms of nuclear safety and long operational lifetime that could exceed 60 years [19].

5. Importance of chromium

Chromium has been included as a critical raw material in 2014 assessment due to greater concentration of supply in main producing countries, combined with more detailed statistics for the smaller producers. Chromium is just over the supply risk threshold and could be considered a borderline case (Figure 5). The recycling rate is low and there are limited options for substitution, particularly in its main application, i.e. in stainless steel. The majority of EU's chromium originates

from third countries (88%), mainly from South Africa and Kazakhstan; just less than 3% of the world production takes place in EU. The forecast average annual demand growth to 2020 for chromium is around 4.2% per year and it is evaluated that supply and demand in chromium market to 2020 would be balanced [9]. According to United States Geologic Survey chromium has no substitute in stainless steel, the leading end use, or in super-alloys, the major strategic end use [29].

6. Nuclear energy in Bulgaria

Unit 1 of “Kozloduy” NPP was connected to the national grid on 24 July 1974, thus making Bulgaria the first country in South-eastern Europe and the eleventh country in the world to operate a nuclear power station [20]. The total operational experience of Bulgaria as of 31 December 2014 amounts to 157 reactor-years and 3 reactor-months [15].

At the moment, the installed nuclear capacity is 2000 MW in two units (Units 5 and 6) with reactors WWER-1000/V-320 at the “Kozloduy” NPP site. Each reactor has nameplate thermal power of 3000 MW and nameplate electric power of 1000 MW [2]. The total power production of “Kozloduy” NPP for the period 24 July 1974 – 31 December 2015 is 570 TWh [21].

Nuclear power is the second most important electricity generating technology in Bulgarian power system beside lignite-fired thermal power stations. For the 2005-2014 timeframe nuclear energy has contributed to between 33.5% and 43.1% of Bulgarian electricity generation. In 2015 the net nuclear generated electricity is 14.3 TWh (approximately 32.2% of Bulgarian net generation) [7].

Currently the Bulgarian nuclear programme includes lifetime extension of the existing units 5 and 6 at “Kozloduy” NPP [28], decommissioning of units 1-4 at “Kozloduy” NPP [25], and construction of unit 7 at “Kozloduy” NPP [3]. Nuclear energy will be maintained and developed as a key power generating technology; this includes both units 5 and 6 operational lifetime extension and constructing new units with installed capacity of up to 2000 MW [6].

Moreover, nuclear power in Bulgaria is highly reliable – the average load factor of “Kozloduy” NPP for the period 2007-2015 is 86.35% [23]; that value being substantially higher than the world average for PWR units with installed capacity of over 600 MWe, which is 77% [15]. When compared with other power generating technologies nuclear power’s importance for maintaining the power system’s reliability becomes obvious. In 2015 nuclear power’s installed capacity was 16.26% (2080 MW) of total power generating capacity but generated 31.24% of the power, ranking second after thermal power plants (49.91%) and before hydropower (12.62%), and renewable energy sources (6.23%). Nuclear power has the highest load factor (84.4%) which is much higher than other energy sources’ load factors – 58.6% for lignite and brown coal-fired plants, 22.2% for hydropower, 23.9% for wind power, and 15.3% for photovoltaics [10].

Considering the mid-term perspective for a new nuclear unit construction, the anticipated power demand should be taken into account. The national transmission system operator (ESO) in its scenarios for grid development anticipates that the annual power consumption would rise between 5.2% and 9.6% by 2025 on 2016 basis. According to their analyses, new nuclear unit wouldn’t be needed prior 2035; however, additional nuclear capacity would come from power uprates of the present units that would be carried out as a part of the operational lifetime extension programme [4].

Based on climate change mitigation policies promoted by the European Union during the COP21 conference there are already several forecasts about nuclear power’s role in the future Bulgarian electric system – Bulgarian Energy and Mining Forum’s assessments are that it would be 40% in 2030 and 52% in 2050 [12], while Energy Management Institute’s projections show that nuclear power might generate 20,148 GWh (36.9% of total production) in 2050 [5], this figure representing a 40.85% increase compared with the 2015 value (14,305 GWh). Thus, nuclear power would have the largest share in Bulgaria’s power generation. The goal of extending operational life of Units 5 and 6 with 30 years (to 2037 and 2039 respectively) fully corresponds with these projections.

II. Research motivation

The aim of the proposed research plan is to gain understanding on the role of CRMs in nuclear industry; that requires clarification of the specifics of the system material-coolant-working parameters by investigating corrosion of construction materials exposed to working conditions in “Kozloduy” nuclear power plant in Bulgaria. Samples of construction materials of importance for the reliable and safe long-term operation of NPPs with light-water reactors were investigated.

Currently, KNPP is undergoing operational life-time extension programme that is scheduled to end in 2019. Its aim is to extend the service life of the two operational power units, which were commissioned in 1987 and 1992 respectively, by 30 years (2047 and 2049 respectively). One of the tasks associated with the life-time extension programme is determining the corrosion rate of key construction materials under operating conditions. Such material is 08X18H10T type of steel.

1. WWER-1000 secondary circuit water chemistry

Currently “Kozloduy” NPP (KNPP) consists of two power units that operate pressurised light water reactors of Russian design WWER-1000/V230 with 1000 MW gross electric output each. This reactor type is analogous to the Western designed PWR reactor type. WWER-1000 operates in two-circuit system which means that the coolant circulating through the reactor core (primary circuit) transfers the heat to the working fluid (feed water) of the secondary circuit indirectly through a steam generator, ensuring any radioactivity remains within the primary circuit (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Primary and secondary circuits of WWER-1000 nuclear power unit (general scheme)

The two circuits have different water chemistries because of the different physicochemical conditions they operate under. There are two main goals that the secondary circuit water chemistry regime must achieve:

1. Minimize sludge deposition in the steam generators;
2. Minimize the corrosion rate of all construction materials used in the secondary circuit's components (condensers, feed water preheaters, de-aerators, etc.).

The water chemistry in the secondary circuit must ensure:

- Minimal salt deposits on steam generators' tubes, steam turbine's blades, and condensate and feed water circuits;
- Prevention of corrosive and corrosive-erosive damage on steam generators', pipelines', and other equipment's construction materials;
- Overall minimization of salt concentration in feed water, especially chlorides and sulphites;

- Low oxygen concentration in condensate and feed water;
- Stable feed water pH.

The main sources for secondary circuit water contamination are:

- Not very well purified supplemental water;
- Air suction through not well sealed sections of the secondary circuit operating under vacuum;
- Cooling water suction through not well sealed sections in the condenser (the cooling water is not purified natural water that originates from the water body used as heat sink; in the case of the “Kozloduy” NPP that’s the Danube river);
- Corrosion products from secondary circuit construction materials [26].

Historically, the water chemistry regime of the secondary circuit of WWER-1000 nuclear power units was hydrazine-ammoniac. In the recent years the water chemistry has been changed and since 2010 the so called AMETA water chemistry is applied in “Kozloduy” NPP. AMETA stands for ammonia-ethanolamine water chemistry; it maintains feed water’s pH₂₅ between 9.70 and 9.95 with NH₃ concentration of 3000 – 5000 µg/kg and ethanolamine concentration of 300 – 500 mg/kg [22].

2. Steel 08X18H10T

Since “Kozloduy” NPP is designed and built using Russian technology, the eligible construction materials for nuclear power plants applications are outlined in the Russian standard for safe nuclear power equipment operation [27]. One of the main stainless steels used in Russian-designed nuclear power plants is 08X18H10T.

Figure 7. 08X18H10T chemical composition, wt%

08X18H10T is a Soviet/Russian austenitic chromium-nickel steel that is widely used in nuclear power applications. Its composition is regulated by the standard GOST 5632-72 and is as follows [11]:

- Carbon – not more than 0.08 wt%;
- Silicon – not more than 0.80 wt%;
- Manganese – not more than 2.00 wt%;
- Nickel – between 9.00 wt% and 11.00 wt%;
- Sulphur – not more than 0.02 wt%;
- Phosphorus – not more than 0.035 wt%;
- Chromium – between 17.00 wt% and 19.00 wt%;
- Copper – not more than 0.30 wt%;
- Titanium – not less than 5 times carbon’s concentration, not more than 0.70 wt%;
- Iron – the remaining part.

Its density is 7900 kg/m^3 . The upper limits for alloying elements and admixtures in 08X18H10T's composition are on figure Figure 7.

III. Results

1. Metallographic studies

The samples are taken from spent fuel storage pool's feed water system. This pool's function is to store under water the spent fuel assemblies after their discharge from the reactor core. This is needed in order to remove the spent fuel's decay heat and serve as an intermediary stage in the back end of the nuclear fuel cycle during which spent fuel's activity decay heat decrease to levels allowing further handling. The materials' state is extremely important in terms of ensuring nuclear safety and economic life-time extension. The working conditions of the material under normal operation of the power plant are listed in Table 1. The pipes were cut across, polished, and etched.

Table 1. Operational conditions of spent fuel cooling pool's feed water system

Working Medium	Chemically Purified Water	
Material	Stainless Steel 08X18H10T	
Working Parameters		
t_{\min}	15.00	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
t_{\max}	45.00	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
p_{\min}	0.20	MPa
p_{\max}	0.60	MPa
pH_{\min}	5.50	
pH_{\max}	8.00	
γ_{\max}	1.00	$\mu\text{S/cm}$
$\text{C}_{\text{Cl-max}}$	0.05	mg/l

The performed microscopic studies on the samples reveal austenitic steel in annealed state. The austenitic structure is saturated with uniformly spread chromium, titanium, and nickel carbides. A uniform and homogenous distribution of elements without segregation can be observed. Microcrystals of carbides and oxides intercepted in different planes are spread into the structure. The composition of the steel corresponds to the standard specification. This is well illustrated by the material characterization (Figure 8 -Figure 10).

Figure 8. SEM Picture of the surface of the characterized material

a) Carbon distribution

b) Chromium distribution

c) Iron distribution

d) Nickel distribution

e) Silicon distribution (its uniformity suggests it might have remained from the polishing process)

f) Titanium distribution

Figure 9. Material chemical composition characterization

Figure 10. Material's spectrum

The grain size of the material was found to be around 3-4 μm (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Grain size of the steel

Figure 12. Material's etched surface

The examination of the steel's etched surface reveals the austenitic phase distribution as well as the distribution of the non-metal phases. Some separates pits due to single non-metal aggregates can

be observed. Initial intergranular stress corrosion is observed on the borders of complex carbides (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Chemical composition of characteristic points on the material cross-section

Figure 14. Tube's inner surface and deposits of impurities characterization

The inner surface of the tubes is covered by a protective layer of chromium and iron oxides, combined with nickel and chromium ferrites, and chromium and iron complex carbides. Deposits of sodium and potassium chlorides, as well as compounds of hardness are identified, most probably coming from water impurities. The composition of deposits was identified by spectroscopic studies. The results are shown on Figure 14.

Because of the long-term operation of the studied material, single changes in initial stage were identified in the microstructure.

2. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) studies of austenitic steel 08X18H10T were performed in test water media with varying concentrations of ammonia at constant concentration of sodium bicarbonate and chlorides at room temperatures. The solutions' composition aimed to simulate some of the conditions that occur in the secondary circuit of the WWER-1000 units that operate in Kozloduy NPP.

EIS is in situ technique to control the constructional material interface layer changes. The impedance is calculated by applying AC voltage in a range of specific frequency values and measuring the current in the electrolytic cell. The experimental tests were performed with varying the pH of the solution. The comparative studies were performed to elucidate the behaviour of the interfacial layer between the steel and the electrolyte in cases of penetrations of chlorides from cooling water, while the ammonium is used commonly in water chemical treatment in second contours of NPPs. Sodium bicarbonate usually is a component of cooling waters. The secondary coolant in a double circuit NPPs is isolated from the cooling water used for steam condensation, but penetration of raw water into condensate happens in a case of pits into the condenser tubes fouling the condensate. Further, the condensate is returned into the steam generator as feed water and negative corrosion impact and scale formation could be provoked. The resistance of the protective layer over the austenitic steel is of key importance for long-term operation of the equipment.

A two electrode cell was prepared for investigation of the metal/electrolyte system. The counter electrode was platinum, and the reference electrode was calomelic. The electrochemical impedance responses were mathematically analysed by Nyquist and Bode plots. An equivalent circuit model was developed to present steel passivation.

The obtained result will be important for future comparison of deposition and investigation of alternative coatings for protection of steel under operation conditions. On the other hand such kind of studies could contribute for maintaining optimal chemical parameters of coolant, in order to guarantee long-term operation of the NPPs and avoid material failures.

Spectra of the impedance of the system under series of frequencies of a sample immersed in an aqueous solution of 5 ppm chlorides, 10 ppm bicarbonate, and variable ammonia concentrations are presented on Figure 15. The pH has been varied from 7.0 to 10.0. Real and imaginary parts of the impedance (Z) were obtained corresponding to the resistance and reactance values. The protective layer behaviour is described by the low-frequency part, while the high-frequency corresponds to the electrolyte characteristics. The Nyquist plot (imaginary versus real impedance) allows calculating polarization resistance and the corresponding corrosion current. In the Bode plot (lg modulus Z versus lg frequency) the horizontal part in the region of high frequencies corresponds to electrolyte resistance. The trend of Z dependences show that the behaviour of studied material at test conditions is in the corrosion control zone. The initial analysis confirms the robustness of 08X18H10T steel which underlines its importance as a main construction material for nuclear power plants equipment. Given the amount of chromium used as an alloying element, it would be difficult to replace this type of steel taking into account its role in systems and equipment critical for guaranteeing nuclear safety. On the other hand, given the optimal water chemistry is observed, 08X18H10T steel would be able to be applied for safe long-term operation of nuclear power plants.

Figure 15. EIS results for a 08X18H10T sample immersed in 5 ppm chlorides, 10 ppm bicarbonate, and variable ammonia concentrations and pH range 7.0 to 10.0

Acknowledgements

I'd like to thank COST Association for the funding that made this research possible.

I'd like to give the recognition due to "Kozloduy" Nuclear Power Plant which provided the samples needed to carry out the analyses presented in this paper.

I am extremely grateful to prof. Maria de Fátima G. Costa Montemor for accepting me as part of her team and giving me the opportunity to execute this short term research mission.

I deeply and sincerely thank Yegor Morozov and Marta Alves; their invaluable help, support, and input proved crucial for the successful completion of this work. I am also thankful to the entire team of the Group for corrosion studies and surface engineering at CQE for making me feel welcome.

I owe most respectful appreciation to assoc. prof. Silviya Boycheva and assoc. prof. Kalin Filipov for encouraging me to undertake this endeavour, and for the support they provided during the application process and the duration of the mission.

References

- [1] BP, Energy Outlook to 2035 (2016)
- [2] BULGARIAN NUCLEAR REGULATORY AGENCY, European Stress Tests. National Report for Bulgaria's Progress. Kozloduy NPP, Sofia (September 2011) (in Bulgarian)

- [3] Consortium Dicon-Acciona Ing., Environmental Impact Assessment Report for Investment Proposal: Building a New Nuclear Unit of the Latest Generation at the Kozloduy NPP Site, Sofia (August 2013)
- [4] ELECTRICITY SYSTEM OPERATOR, Draft Plan for Transmission Network Development for the Period 2016-2025, Sofia, Bulgaria (2016) (in Bulgarian)
- [5] ENERGY MANAGEMENT INSTITUTE, BG 2050 Electricity Generation Structure (EMI based on PRIMES data) (2016), [<http://www.emi-bg.com/bg/chart/57a20a53664a2e659f2f3f71>]
- [6] *Energy Strategy of the Republic of Bulgaria till 2020 for Reliable, Efficient and Cleaner Energy*, Sofia (June 2011)
- [7] ENTSO-E, Statistical Factsheet 2015, ENTSO-E, Brussels (2016)
- [8] EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Communication from the Commission. Nuclear Illustrative Programme presented under Article 40 of the Euratom Treaty for the opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee, COM(2016)177, Brussels (2016)
- [9] EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Report on Critical Raw Materials for the EU (May 2014)
- [10] Georgiev A. *et al.*, Statistical data and indicators for electricity generation in Bulgaria in 2015, *Energetika* 6 (2016) 28-37 (in Bulgarian)
- [11] GOST 5632-72 (ГОСТ 5632-72, Стали высоколегированные и сплавы коррозионностойкие, жаростойкие и жаропрочные. Марки, УДК 669.15-194:006.354) (1972)
- [12] Hinovski I., The New International Policy Documents Adopted in 2015 and the Ensuing New Conditions for Bulgaria's Economic Development 2030-2050, Bulgarian Energy and Mining Forum, Seminar "New Guidelines for Bulgaria's Energy Development by 2030-2050", 21.01.2016, Kozloduy NPP, Kozloduy, Bulgaria (2016) (in Bulgarian)
- [13] IAEA, Climate Change and Nuclear Power 2016, Vienna (2016)
- [14] IAEA, Energy, Electricity and Nuclear Power Estimates for the Period up to 2050, Reference Data Series No. 1, Vienna (2016)
- [15] IAEA, Nuclear Power Reactors in the World, Reference Data Series No. 2, Vienna (2016)
- [16] IAEA, Power Reactor Information System (PRIS) [<https://www.iaea.org/pris/>], accessed 22.02.2017
- [17] IAEA, Safe Long Term Operation of Nuclear Power Plants, Safety Reports Series No.57, Vienna (2008)
- [18] IEA, Energy, Climate Change and Environment: 2016 Insights, Paris (2016)
- [19] Konings, R. J. M. (ed.), Comprehensive Nuclear Materials, Elsevier, Amsterdam, Oxford, Waltham, MA (2012)
- [20] KOZLODUY NPP, 40 Years Kozloduy NPP, ISBN 978-954-90852-3-5 (2014)
- [21] KOZLODUY NPP, Annual Report 2015 (2015) (in Bulgarian)
- [22] Minkova K., Water Chemistry Types in Nuclear Power Plants and their Effects on Reliability and Safe Operation, Kozloduy NPP, Seminar "Nuclear Power in Bulgaria and Worldwide" (2017) (in Bulgarian)
- [23] Naydenov I., K. Filipov, Assessment of the Effects of Linking WWER-1000's and AP1000's Fuel Cycles, *In: Proceedings of International Symposium "Energetics 2016", Book 1*, Ohrid, Macedonia (2016) 117-125
- [24] OECD NEA, Challenges in Long-term Operation of Nuclear Power Plants, OECD No. 7074, Paris (2012)
- [25] *Revised Strategy for Spent Nuclear Fuel and Radioactive Waste Management by 2030*, Sofia (2015) (in Bulgarian)
- [26] Roshchektaev B. M., Water Chemistry of NPPs with Reactors WWER-1000 and RBMK-1000, National Nuclear University МЭФІ, Moscow (2010) (in Russian)
- [27] Rules for safe design and operation of nuclear power plants' equipment and piping (in Russian) (ПИНАЭ Г-7-008-89 Правила устройства и безопасной эксплуатации оборудования и трубопроводов атомных энергетических установок) (1989)
- [28] Stanimirov B., Extension of the operational time of units 5 and 6 of NPP Kozloduy – licensee status, BULATOM 2016, Varna, Bulgaria (2016)
- [29] U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY, Mineral Commodity Summaries (January 2016)
- [30] US EIA, International Energy Outlook 2016 with Projections to 2040, DOE/EIA-0484(2016), Washington, DC (2016)